

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Animal Feed Science and Technology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/anifeedsci

Why pond farmed carp remain poor in EPA+DHA despite rich food and genetic repertoire: Evidence from pond food-web and fatty acid supply dynamics

Bidipta Mandal, Ales Tomcala, Deepali Rahi Roy, Jan Mraz, Koushik Roy ^{*}

University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses, Institute of Aquaculture and Protection of Waters, České Budějovice 370 05, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Plankton consortia
Omega-3 fatty acids
EPA and DHA
Pond feeds
Omega-3 sparing effect
Semi-intensive aquaculture
Freshwater food web

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the dynamics of omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 LCPUFA) in European fishponds, with a focus on the ecological and nutritional factors governing eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, 20:5n-3) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22:6n-3) availability and poor accumulation in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). In a series of 9 experimental fishponds over one full vegetative season, we analyzed the food web and ecosystem processes. The carp gill-filterable plankton consortia ($\geq 200 \mu\text{m}$ mesh) is a rich source of EPA+DHA: $1785.8 \pm 479.3 \text{ mg } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$ (annual mean), whereas the zoobenthos is a lesser-rich source: $622.7 \pm 496.6 \text{ mg EPA+DHA } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$. Natural food is the only n-3 LCPUFA source for pond carp (as supplementary feed has 0 %). Seasonal analyses showed a peak in lipid and n-3 LC PUFA availability during the early growing season (May–July), followed by their marked decline in the end season (August–October). Principal component analysis confirmed that these are tightly linked (positively correlated) with cladoceran abundance and negatively linked with chlorophyll-a concentration and fish biomass density. The EPA and DHA availability peaked at the beginning season, particularly during June–July ($13.15 \pm 3.40 \mu\text{g EPA l}^{-1}$; $5.72 \pm 3.40 \mu\text{g DHA l}^{-1}$), while the lowest values ($4.63 \pm 5.27 \mu\text{g EPA l}^{-1}$; $2.04 \pm 2.02 \mu\text{g DHA l}^{-1}$) were observed throughout the final three months before harvest or end season (August–October). The minimum physiological requirement of the essential n-3 fatty acid for carp, alpha-linolenic acid (ALA, 18:3n-3), was not fulfilled in the final three months before harvest (see supply-demand model). Final harvested carp in November showed $158.07 \pm 3.79 \text{ mg EPA+DHA } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ wet weight}$ ($547.98 \pm 102.64 \text{ mg } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$), indicating that merely 45 % of EPA+DHA concentration factor was transferred from zooplankton-benthos DM to fish DM. Our findings indicate that the low EPA+DHA concentration in carp flesh is due to: (1) missing EPA and DHA in diet for three months before harvest, and (2) deficiency of essential ALA for three months before harvest. As a result, under present European pond feeding management, both accumulation and *de-novo* biosynthesis of n-3 LCPUFA in pond carp is severely compromised. Alternative feed and feeding management have been proposed.

* Correspondence to: Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, , Na Sadkach 1780, Ceske Budejovice 370 05, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: kroy@frov.jcu.cz (K. Roy).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2026.116678>

Received 12 January 2026; Accepted 29 January 2026

Available online 30 January 2026

0377-8401/© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 LCPUFA) intake, such as eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), are indispensable for overall human health (especially cardiac health), as humans cannot or negligibly biosynthesize them (Zárate et al., 2017). Landlocked central European countries (no immediate sovereign access to the sea) have been exhibiting a low omega-3 index (O3I: <6 %) in the adult population (Schuchardt et al., 2024). For example, in Czechia (representative of typical Central Europe), low O3I contributes to an average of ~50 % of total annual deaths due to cardiovascular diseases (OECD/European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2017). While, Central Eastern European Region (CEER) fishponds or European fishponds in short are reported as the potential reservoirs of an untapped source of physiologically important lipids (harvesting potential of ~278 tons EPA + DHA year⁻¹) (Roy et al., 2025). Since the medieval period, these ponds have been deeply ingrained in European heritage, and the common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) has been predominantly bred and cultured in these ponds for centuries (Roy et al., 2023b, 2022). Unlike ponds from other parts of the world (Asian commercial ponds average – 0.15–12.83 ha in size) (Gordon and Bjørndal, 2009), these are large (ranging from 2 to 300 ha) and resemble temperate shallow lake ecosystems (depth 1–4 m) (Roy et al., 2023b, 2022). A recent study estimated that CEER represents 0.25 million hectares of pond area, which currently yields 0.12 million tons of pond carp annually and has been providing ecosystem services worth ~2375 € ha⁻¹ (Roy et al., 2025). However, these ponds are highly monitored by the EU directive on water frameworks. Unlike other continents, the external application of fertilizers is prohibited, and supplementary feeding is also regulated (Roy et al., 2022). Currently, carp are being cultured semi-intensively in these ponds (stocking density: 0.2–0.4 tons ha⁻¹) in CEER ponds, for instance, the carp production cycle in Czech ponds starts in spring (April–March), soon after the thaw, and extends up to autumn (October–November). At the beginning of the vegetative season (April–May), no supplementary feed is added to the ponds; fish solely rely on natural food, followed by supplementation with cereals (typically, wheat, corn, etc.) from mid to end of the vegetative season (June–October). Average production ranged between 0.5–1.5 ton ha⁻¹, with the feed conversion ratio (FCR) of ~3 in the presence of natural food (Roy et al., 2023b).

These ponds are also reported to exhibit omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 PUFA) rich plankton consortia (Mraz et al., 2012), which are not directly accessible to human consumption but can be upcycled through aquaculture (Roy et al., 2025), as fish often mirror their diets' fatty acid composition (Mraz and Pickova, 2011; Xu et al., 2020). Lower trophic level fish, such as cyprinids (e. g., carp), possess a higher trophic transfer efficiency of omega-3 LCPUFAs from the fish food web compared to higher trophic fish (predatory) (Kainz et al., 2017). Meanwhile, CEER Ponds exclusively produce these cyprinids (carp) (almost 70 % of the total EU carp production), led by Poland (21600 tons year⁻¹), followed by the Czech Republic (20401 tons year⁻¹), Hungary (12300 tons year⁻¹), and Germany (10000 tons year⁻¹) (Roy et al., 2023b). It is also noteworthy that several studies have also reported that cyprinids, especially carp, have the capability to desaturate and elongate short chain PUFAs (e.g., alpha linolenic acid or ALA) to LCPUFAs (Pilecky et al., 2022; Roy et al., 2023b). Additionally, pond carps are not the consumers but the net producers of omega-3 LCPUFAs (e. g., EPA and DHA) because there is no input of EPA and DHA by grain feeding from the human technosphere (Mraz et al., 2025; Roy et al., 2023a). Despite this huge potential (as omega-3 vectors from plankton to humans) and having a majority share (24 %) in the annual fish food plate, pond carp only contributes 2.85 % of the total daily omega-3 LCPUFA supply to the central European population (Czechia). It may be due to their low absolute EPA+DHA concentration (<250 mg EPA+DHA 100 g⁻¹ fillet) (Linhartová et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2023a). The reason behind the low LCPUFA concentration (in traditional carp fillet) has been addressed as no or negligible supply of LCPUFAs through supplementary feeding (wheat fed traditional farming) (Mraz et al., 2025; Pilecky et al., 2022). However, insights from gut content analysis, carp's prey item majorly consists of zooplankton (majorly, cladocera, followed by copepods) and debris, followed by zoobenthos (including insect larvae) in the Czech pond (Anton-Pardo et al., 2014). Hence, the fact cannot be ignored that (apart from LCPUFA-deficient supplementary feeding), although plankton consortia are a good source of omega-3 PUFAs (Mráz et al., 2012) and a major natural food for carp, the fish cannot retain natural food driven-PUFAs. In this study, we investigated the probable cause of poor LCPUFA retention efficiency in pond-grown carps and aimed to conceptualize the omega-3 LCPUFA mining strategy from CEER ponds based on the findings.

The carp's fatty acid is diet sensitive, and a bioenergetic mismatch could result in loss of these FAs during trophic transfer. Additionally, a low LCPUFA (EPA+DHA in food) condition could lead to biosynthesis of EPA in carp from precursor fatty acid ALA (18:3n-3) (Monroig et al., 2022). Furthermore, a lower availability of the precursor ALA could also limit the EPA+DHA, eventually impacting the trophic upgradation of short-chain omega-3 PUFA. We suspected the occurrence of such phenomena in CEER ponds (traditional carp farming). To evaluate these assumptions, a multidisciplinary approach integrating fish nutrition knowledge and pond ecology is required. This necessitates a detailed investigation into the seasonal availability of natural prey-associated lipid and fatty acids, a critical gap that, to the best of our knowledge, remains unaddressed for CEER ponds. This understanding is crucial for optimizing the farming approach to harvest omega-3 LCPUFAs from the pond for the human food system.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental ponds and design

A set of nine identical earthen fishponds (each 0.16 ha in area, mean depth 0.8 m, drainable), located at the experimental pond facility of the University of South Bohemia in Vodňany, Czechia (49°09'24.9"N, 14°09'54.2"E; 404 m a.s.l.), was monitored in this observational study from May to October 2024. The ponds were pre-drained and left to overwinter (November 2023–February 2024) before being gradually refilled with water from a nearby natural freshwater stream in March 2024. No fish were introduced during this period to allow plankton development. In April 2024, each pond was stocked with 2 + year-old scaly common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) at

a density of 471.3 kg ha⁻¹, with an initial body weight (BW) of 384.82 ± 3.47 g and total length (TL) of 275.29 ± 0.93 mm. By November 2024 (harvesting), the carp reached a final BW of 1502.61 ± 12.86 g and TL of 426.03 ± 1.22 mm.

There were two groups of ponds receiving supplementary feeding. Group-1 ponds (n = 3) received wheat by hand feeding throughout the season (April to October), following the traditional European pond feeding approach (Roy et al., 2023b, 2022). Group-2 ponds (n = 6) received wheat only during beginning of season (April-June) and an extruded pellet made up of low opportunity cost biomass (LOCB; local crop by-products) during end of season (July-October), following the balanced pond feeding concept (Roy et al., 2023b, 2022). Both group-1 and 2 ponds had received equal amount of feed till the end of experiment following a fixed month feeding plan: April (3 %), May (7 %), June (11 %), July (32 %), August (25 %), September (15 %), and October (7 %) of annual dose (563 kg pond⁻¹). The ponds were supplied with low-lipid supplementary feeds: whole grain wheat (protein: 9.5 %, lipid: 1.23 %, starch 67.9 %, neutral detergent fiber 9.9 %, gross energy 354.1 kcal 100 g⁻¹) and a LOCB plant-based pellet (protein: 22.7 %, lipid: 2.37 %, neutral detergent fiber 21.1 %, gross energy 256.5 kcal 100 g⁻¹). The LOCB plant-pellet had the following recipe: Wheat (28 %), rapeseed expeller, solvent extracted (40 %), sunflower expeller meal, dehulled, solvent extracted (14 %), morning cereals factory discards, extruded waste (14 %), corn distiller's dried grains with solubles (3 %), and rapeseed oil (1 %).

No manuring was applied during the growing season. Among the ponds, three replicates (n = 3) were exclusively fed wheat (563 kg pond⁻¹) from April to October, while the remaining six replicates (n = 6) received wheat (123 kg pond⁻¹) from April to June and plant-based pellets (432 kg pond⁻¹) from July to October. The pellets were formulated in-house using non-refined agri-food by-products. Despite the contrasting feeding regimes, no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed between the two pond groups in lipid, EPA, DHA, ALA, total omega-3, total omega-6 fatty acids, and dry matter (DM) concentrations in carp gill-filterable plankton consortia across the season. This is further elaborated in results sub-chapter. Consequently, the data were analyzed collectively (n = 9 ponds). Monthly sampling was conducted for carp's gill filterable Plankton consortia collection, and fish biometrics; additionally, limnological parameters, including total nitrogen (TN), dissolved organic carbon (DOC), total phosphorus (TP), temperature (T), pH, and chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) were also recorded monthly according to Kajgrova et al. (Kajgrová et al., 2022) and Vrba et al. (Vrba et al., 2024).

2.2. Plankton sampling

Zooplankton abundance was quantified by collecting integrated water samples from the surface layer (0–0.5 m depth) using a van Dorn sampler (3.2 L volume, 0.5 m length). Sampling was conducted at twelve equidistant points along a linear transect in the pelagic zone of each pond to ensure spatial representativeness. The combined sample was poured into pre-cleaned 50 L plastic containers and was processed for zooplankton assessment. Samples were fixed in 4 % formaldehyde solution. Zooplankton were identified to the lowest practical taxonomic level and enumerated microscopically in the laboratory.

In this study, carp gill-filterable plankton consortia (simply, plankton consortia) refer to the Collective biomass of Zooplankton, bacteria, algae, etc., that can be filtered by the fish gill during their natural feeding practice. Plankton consortia were collected via vertical plankton net hauls (mesh size: 200 µm), followed by sieving > 2357 µm mesh to remove debris. The selection of the mesh size was intended to target plankton consortia ingestible (can be sieved through gill) by juvenile to adult carp. It corresponds directly to the carp's branchial sieving capacity (>250 µm) (Hasan and Macintosh, 1992; Sibbing, 1988), thereby ensuring the collected food particles are nutritionally relevant to carp nutrition.

The volume of water filtered by the plankton net was estimated using the formula: $V = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \times l$, where d is the diameter of the net mouth (dm), l is the hauling distance (dm), and the result is the volume (V) in liters (L). Approximately 900 liters of water were filtered per pond per sampling event. Samples were immediately placed in an insulated box with ice, transported to the laboratory, lyophilized (14 h main drying + 10 h final drying), and stored at -80 °C until further analysis. The dry matter percentage (DM%) was calculated using the following equation: $DM\% = (DW / WW) \times 100$, where WW represents the wet weight prior to lyophilization and DW denotes the dry weight post-lyophilization. Dry matter, lipid, and fatty acids availability (per liter) were computed with respect to the amount (liters) of water filtered during sampling.

The length of the freeze-dried Planktons was measured using a Stereo microscope SZX16 (Olympus, Japan), and individual dry weight was measured gravimetrically using a precision microbalance (Mettler Toledo XP2U Excellence Plus XP Ultra Micro Balances 2 g x 0.1Ug, Germany).

2.3. Limnological parameters and fish sampling

We measured monthly key physical and chemical water parameters in each fishpond. Manual in situ measurements of temperature were taken 20 cm below the surface three times per week using a portable multimeter (HI98494, Hanna Instruments, USA). Water temperature was also recorded continuously at hourly intervals using two data loggers (Minikin-T, EMS Brno) placed in the surface and bottom layers of each pond. Samples for nutrient and organic matter analysis, including total phosphorus (TP), total nitrogen (TN), chlorophyll a (Chl-a), and dissolved organic carbon (DOC), were collected and analyzed by an accredited laboratory (Povodí Vltavy, Č. Budějovice) using standardized protocols. TP was determined spectrophotometrically using the ammonium molybdate method (ČSN EN ISO 6878, 2005). TN was measured via high-temperature catalytic oxidation and electrochemical detection (ČSN EN 12260, 2004). Only DOC samples were pre-processed in situ using 0.45 µm nylon syringe filters to separate bacteria and other microorganisms. In each sampling campaign, 20–25 fish were measured for individual total length (TL in mm) and body weight (BW in g) across nine ponds on the same day, to check the monthly progression of growth and density. These methodological standards and details are

further clarified in Kajgrova et al. (Kajgrová et al., 2022) and Vrba et al. (Vrba et al., 2024)

2.4. Lipid classes and fatty acid analysis

The lipid extraction was performed according to the method of (Hara and Radin, 1978) with slight modification (Mraz and Pickova, 2009). Briefly, approximately 0.2 g of dry plankton consortia samples were homogenized in 5 ml of hexane: isopropanol (3:2, v:v) (HIP) using BeatBUG® vials and a BeatBUG® homogenizer (45 sec at 4000 rpm). Post-homogenization, 3 ml of Na₂SO₄ solution was added, followed by centrifugation (Trigon-Plus®) at 5000 rpm (18°C, 5 min). The upper lipid-containing supernatant was carefully transferred to pre-weighed tubes. The step was repeated after adding 1 ml of hexane to the centrifuge tube, and the remaining precipitate/pellet and liquid were discarded. Subsequently, the lipid-containing liquid was evaporated using nitrogen gas. Lipid content was determined gravimetrically using a precision microbalance (Mettler Toledo XP2U Excellence Plus XP Ultra Micro Balances 2 g x 0.1Ug, Germany).

Lipid methylation was catalyzed using boron trifluoride-methanol complex solution with NaOH according to (Appelqvist, 1968). FAME C 23:0 served as the internal standard. Fatty acid composition was determined by gas chromatography (Trace Ultra FID; Thermo Scientific, Milan, Italy) equipped with a BPX-70 fused silica capillary column (50 m length × 0.22 mm internal diameter, 0.25 µm film thickness; SGE, USA). The temperature program initiated at 70°C (hold 0.5 min), ramped at 30°C min⁻¹ to 150°C, then increased at 1.5°C min⁻¹ to 220°C (final hold 11 min), totaling 60 min analysis time. The PVT injector and detector were maintained at 170°C and 260°C, respectively. Peak identification and quantification were performed using Thermo Xcalibur 3.0.63 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.) by comparing retention times and peak areas against a 7-point calibration curve (15–1000 µg ml⁻¹) generated from the Supelco 37 Component FAME Mix standard (Sigma-Aldrich).

A subset of extracted lipids, irrespective of the pond but was pooled month-wise. 5 µl from each pond sample was mixed and vortexed and was used as a monthly representative for lipid class analysis. Intact lipids in lipidic extract were separated by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) to determine the composition of the different lipid and phospholipid classes. Precoated silica gel 60 TLC plates (20 cm × 10 cm; 0.20 mm layer; Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) were used as the stationary phase. The analysis was performed according to Olsen and Henderson (1989) (Olsen and Henderson, 1989) with modifications. The TLC plates were pre-developed to the full length (85 mm) by placing the plate in the developing chamber Twin Through Chamber 10 × 20 (Camag Switzerland) and using mobile phase hexane-diethyl ether-acetic acid (85:15:1, v/v). Then the plate was placed at 110°C for one hour to activate it. For further use, the plates were stored in an excicator.

Samples were prepared in vials at an approximate concentration of 1 µg ml⁻¹ in chloroform: methanol solution (2:1). Samples were applied to the TLC plates using a Camag ATS 4 automatic TLC sample (Camag Switzerland). The lipid classes were separated by placing the TLC plate in the development chamber Twin Through Chamber 10 × 20 (Camag Switzerland). Firstly, phospholipid classes were separated with a mobile phase consisting of 25 ml methyl-acetate, 25 ml isopropanol, 25 ml chloroform, 10 ml methanol, and 10 ml 0.25 % KCl, developing 69 mm. Then hexane-diethyl ether-acetic acid (85:15:1, v/v) was used for the separation of nonpolar lipid classes, developing 80 mm. After drying, the plate was sprayed in the derivatization chamber Camag Derivatizer (Camag, Switzerland) heavily with copper acetate-phosphoric acid solution (3 g (CH₃COO)₂Cu, 8 ml concentrated phosphoric acid, 92 ml ddH₂O) by red nozzle set to level 4. The plate was then heated at 160°C for 30 min on TLC plate heater III (Camag Switzerland) and then cooled to room temperature. The proportions of the different classes of lipids were measured densitometrically by use of the Camag TLC scanner 3 (Camag Switzerland) using WinCats (Camag Switzerland) software. Lipid classes were identified by comparing the samples with external phospholipid standards and with mixed standards TLC 18-3 A and TLC 18-5 C (Nu-Check Prep, Elysian, Minnesota, USA).

2.5. Essential fatty acid (alpha-linolenic acid, ALA 18:3n-3) requirement and supply modelling

Fish cannot synthesize ALA from any precursor, and must be provided via diet; this is why it is also called an essential fatty acid (EFA). The ALA has been recognized as an EFA for carp, and 0.5 % in the diet is the minimum physiological requirement (NRC, 1993). At whole pond level (*i.e.*, total water volume, and total fish stock), we have computed the daily demand and supply of ALA by carp from its natural (plankton consortia and zoobenthos) and supplementary (wheat) food in the pond from May to October. For ALA supply estimation in the model, zoobenthos fatty acid data from a previous dataset (2022–2023) collected in the same experimental ponds were incorporated alongside the 2024 plankton consortia ALA data. This approach ensured continuity and supported the robustness of the proposed EFA model for pond carp. Per m³ cubical cross-section of the pond, plankton consortia are available more steadily at 0.98–1.28 g DM (interquartile range, IQR), while zoobenthos are available 0.28–1.31 g DM (IQR) being more volatile food source. The lower end of zoobenthos IQR coincides with second half of the season (June onwards), thus contributing negligibly to carp's natural food DM intake for major part of growing season (June to October) (Anton-Pardo et al., 2014; Mraz et al., 2025). In addition, zoobenthos are generally poor in lipids (<5 % DM) compared to plankton consortia (lipid >10 % DM), and their metamorphosis is observed from summer as emergent aquatic insects, or they remain absent in the second half of the vegetative season (carp growing season) (Kajgrova et al., 2021; Mraz et al., 2025; Roy et al., 2023b, 2022).

The volume of the pond water was computed as Volume = Area × Depth, then the cubic meter area was converted into liters of water. The ALA supply from plankton consortia was computed by multiplying the ALA availability (plankton ALA l⁻¹) by the volume of water in the pond (in 1280000 liters). ALA availability was determined by calculating the dry matter yield per liter of filtered water and multiplying it by the sample's alpha-linolenic acid (ALA %DM) content. To calculate the total daily intake of natural food (dry matter) or wheat for the pond, the optimum ration for an individual fish was first set at 2–3 % of its body weight (BW) (NRC, 1993). A rate of 3 % was applied to fish weighing less than 1500 g, and 2 % was applied to those weighing more than 1500 g. This individual intake

value was then multiplied by the total number of fish in the pond (head count) to determine the total daily feed requirement. The monthly averages of fish body weight and water temperature were recorded as follows: May: 546.04 ± 122.39 g and 18.50 ± 0.49 °C, respectively; June: 657.83 ± 136.55 g and 18.64 ± 0.28 °C, respectively; July: 903.91 ± 196.59 g and 23.97 ± 0.60 °C, respectively; August: 1232.60 ± 269.37 g and 22.62 ± 0.33 °C, respectively; September: 1376.39 ± 270.49 g and 22.66 ± 0.29 °C, respectively; and October: 1590.43 ± 336.42 g and 13.47 ± 0.57 °C, respectively. According to the aforementioned monthly average body weight, daily dry matter feed intake was assumed to be 3 % of body weight from May to September, and 2 % in October. The ALA supply from wheat was calculated by multiplying wheat's ALA content (ALA: 0.41 % of DM) by the assumed daily supply/intake. ALA demand for fish was calculated by synthesizing the daily optimum food requirement of the whole biomass (total biomass = average body weight \times head count), multiplying by the minimum ALA requirement percentage (0.5 %) for carp.

Fig. 1. Seasonal dynamics of- (a) cladocera (individual l⁻¹), (b) copepods (individual l⁻¹), (c) dry matter (DM) (mg l⁻¹ pond water), (d) dry matter percentage wet weight, (e) chlorophyll-a, and (f) FMD: fish mass density. (g) Individual dry weight (µg) and (h) length of Zooplankton (µm) in both halves of the vegetative season.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All analyses were conducted using GPT-4o/5 Data Analyst alongside RStudio 2023.12.1 (Build 402). Statistical tests were conducted using GPT-4o/5 Data Analyst. The choice of statistical test (parametric or non-parametric; equal or unequal sample size) was carefully made as per standard statistical recommendations. Principal component analysis (PCA) and all visualizations were generated using RStudio 2023.12.1 (Build 402), which utilized libraries such as “ggplot2”, “tidyverse”, “ggExtra”, “gg4x”, “RColorBrewer”, and “factoextra”. Only Fig. 2e and f were generated using GPT-4o/5 Data Analyst. For temporal trend (monthly) analysis from nine replicated ponds ($n = 9$), box plots were visualized with a LOESS-smoothed trendline. Additionally, the span (6 months; May–October) of fish growing (post-stocking month to pre-harvesting month) was divided (coded) into two halves as “beginning season” (May–July) and “end season” (August–October) to reduce complexity in analysis. The Shapiro–Wilk tests were performed to assess the normality of the data and Levene’s test for homogeneity of variances. Two-variable tests suitable for unequal sample sizes, such as the Welch’s t -test or the Mann–Whitney U test, were performed according to the outcomes of normality test and homogeneity of variances. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed, and a PCA biplot was generated to assess the complex relationship between various limnological parameters and lipids, including polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs). All data in the study are reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Beginning of season implies a month range of May–July, while the end of season implies a month range of August–October, within the pond aquaculture vegetation season typical in CEER.

Fig. 2. Seasonal dynamics of (a) Total lipid ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), (b) ALA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), (c) EPA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), (d) DHA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), (e) Glycolipids (% of lipid), (f) Phosphatidylcholine, Tri-glycerol and cholesterol (% of lipid) – in carp’s gill filterable plankton consortia in pond water.

3. Results

3.1. Plankton community composition and carp gill-filterable planktonic dry matter availability

In the pond water, among the zooplankton groups, copepods' abundance did not show any seasonal trend (Fig. 1b); it was stable across the seasons (71.42 ± 80.40 ind. l^{-1}) and showed no statistical difference ($p > 0.05$) between both halves of the fish growing season. In contrast, cladocera abundance showed an increasing trend from May, peaked during June–July, and collapsed from August till end of season (October) (Fig. 1a). The beginning season (300.19 ± 244.40 ind. l^{-1}) showed a significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher cladocera abundance compared to the end season (32.97 ± 35.92 ind. l^{-1}). A similar seasonal trend (Fig. 1c) as cladocera was also observed for dry matter (DM $mg\ l^{-1}$) availability of carp gill-filterable plankton consortia ($>200\ \mu m$) in pond water. Peaked DM availability was observed during June–July, and low availability was observed (August–October). Overall, the beginning season ($1.03 \pm 0.54\ mg\ l^{-1}$) showed threefold higher ($p < 0.001$) carp gill-filterable DM availability compared to the end season ($0.32 \pm 0.26\ mg\ l^{-1}$).

An increasing trend (Fig. 1f) in chlorophyll-a (chl-a) concentration was observed from May to September, followed by a drop in October. Compared to the beginning season ($68.89 \pm 23.09\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$), significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher concentrations ($126.26 \pm 59.85\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$) were observed at the end of the season, particularly peaking in August–September. Additionally, fish mass density (FMD) increased steadily from the beginning to the end of the vegetative season (Fig. 1e); consequently, FMD was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) at the end of the season ($160.64 \pm 19.29\ g\ m^{-3}$) compared to the beginning ($80.49 \pm 17.81\ g\ m^{-3}$).

3.2. Dry matter content of plankton consortia and morphometrics of zooplankton

Early beginning season (May), plankton consortia showed relatively higher DM% and showed a decreasing trend as the season progressed (Fig. 1d). The DM% at the end season ($5.76 \pm 1.03\ %\ DM$) still significantly lower ($p < 0.001$) than beginning season months ($7.24 \pm 0.92\ %\ DM$). In addition to this, the length–weight analysis revealed that the zooplankton (a major component of the plankton consortia) did not differ ($p > 0.05$) in length, but body weight differed significantly ($p < 0.001$). The beginning season ($143.8 \pm 136.8\ \mu g$) showed significantly higher dry weight individuals compared to the end season ($75.9 \pm 111.5\ \mu g$) (Fig. 1g & h).

3.3. Lipids and lipid classes

Lipid availability (Lipid $\mu g\ l^{-1}$) showed an increasing trend from May and peaked during June–July, followed by a drop in August, till the end of season (Fig. 2a). Availability of lipids is significantly higher in the beginning season window ($110.45 \pm 59.61\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$, $p < 0.001$), whereas the lipid availability in the end season can be as low as $31.49 \pm 29.54\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$.

Among the lipid classes (% of total lipid), phosphatidylcholine showed an upward trend (May to October), while triacylglycerol showed an opposite downward trend with the season's progress. However, cholesterol showed strict homeostasis ($11.87 \pm 0.84\ %$) throughout the season (Fig. 2f). Furthermore, glycolipids (monogalactodiacylglycerol + digalactodiacylglycerol), were also observed in the plankton consortia, which showed a peak in June and decreased steadily from July to October. At the beginning season ($7.27 \pm 1.74\ %$ of lipid), glycolipids were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) compared to end season ($3.22 \pm 0.67\ %$ of lipid) (Fig. 2e).

3.4. Omega-3 fatty acids

Among omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), ALA (C18:3n-3) and EPA (C20:5n-3) showed a similar trend in availability (per liter of water) throughout the vegetative season. Both EPA and ALA showed moderate availability in May, peaked shortly during June–July, and started deteriorating from August (Fig. 2b & c). The beginning season (ALA: $13.88 \pm 7.52\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$, EPA: $11.89 \pm 6.13\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$) showed significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher availability of these fatty acids (FAs) compared to the end season (ALA: $3.53 \pm 3.81\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$, EPA: $4.63 \pm 5.27\ \mu g\ l^{-1}$). DHA (C22:6n-3) exhibited a slightly different trend compared to EPA and ALA. It showed lower availability in May ($0.75 \pm 0.42\ \mu g\ DHA\ l^{-1}$) and peaked during June–July ($5.72 \pm 3.40\ \mu g\ DHA\ l^{-1}$), followed by a drop throughout the end season (August–October: $2.036 \pm 2.02\ \mu g\ DHA\ l^{-1}$) (Fig. 2d). The EPA is present in greater amounts than DHA

Fig. 3. Seasonal dynamics of (a) n-3: n-6 ratio and (b) (SFA+MUFA):(EPA+DHA) ratio of gill-filterable plankton consortia.

throughout the season, while ALA and EPA amounts can be equal.

3.5. Lipid and fatty stoichiometry

3.5.1. n-3: n-6 PUFA ratio

A decreasing trend in the ratio of n-3 to n-6 was observed from May to July (beginning season); conversely, it showed an increasing trend from August to October (end season) (Fig. 3a). The lowest n-3 to n-6 ratios were observed during July and August, while the peak occurred in October. However, the end season (4.42 ± 1.48) exhibited a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher ratio compared to the beginning season (3.66 ± 0.80).

3.5.2. EPA and DHA sparing ratio

The seasonal trend of the (SFA+MUFA): (EPA+DHA) ratio (higher value indicates higher sparing of EPA+DHA from catabolism) showed consistent and significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher values (4.02 ± 0.55) at the beginning of the season (May–July), followed by a drop throughout the end season (2.34 ± 0.59) (Fig. 3b).

3.6. Supply and demand model of essential omega-3 fatty acid (18:3n-3)

May to June showed significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher supply from natural food (plankton consortia + zoobenthos) compared to carp ALA demand, despite accounting for wheat-driven ALA supply. While July showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between demand and total supply (including wheat-driven ALA) or supply from natural food. However, from August onwards, that is, three months prior to harvesting, a significant ($p < 0.001$) supply–demand gap of ALA emerges for pond carp; wheat supply at the optimum feeding rate, in the presence of natural food, cannot also bridge the gap. These months (August to October) exhibited an extremely low supply of ALA, failing to meet the minimum physiological requirement of this essential fatty acid for carp (Fig. 4). The detailed fatty acid profile (FAME% of total fatty acids) and lipid content ($\text{g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$), expressed as mean \pm SD of the observed samples (plankton consortia, zoobenthos, supplementary feed, carp fillets) in the study, is provided in Table 1.

In this study, on dry matter basis, carp gill-filterable consortia exhibited $1785.8 \pm 479.3 \text{ mg EPA+DHA } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$ (annual mean). Comparatively, the zoobenthos exhibit less EPA+DHA $622.7 \pm 496.6 \text{ mg } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$. Whereas, carps (November harvesting) showed only $547.98 \pm 102.64 \text{ mg } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ DM}$ ($158.07 \pm 3.79 \text{ mg EPA+DHA } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ on fresh weight basis), indicating that only 45 % of EPA+DHA concentration factor could be transferred from zooplankton-benthos DM to fish DM. Present result suggests that such low concentration in carp flesh can be due to: (1) missing EPA and DHA in diet for three months before harvest, and (2) absence of essential fatty acid ALA (pre-cursor of EPA) in sufficient physiological quantity for three months before harvest, disabling any endogenous bioconversion efforts in carp.

Fig. 4. Seasonal ALA Supply from carp gill filterable plankton consortia, Zoobenthos, and wheat supplement vs. carp's ALA demand in CEER ponds (Error bars with 95 % confidence interval).

Table 1

Fatty acid profile of Plankton consortia, Zoobenthos, Supplementary feeds (wheat and LOCB pellet), carp fillets, and their lipid content. Values are expressed as mean \pm SD. "NS" denotes the FAs that were not studied, and "-" represents undetected FAs. FAME: fatty acid methyl ester.

FAME [%]	Plankton consortia (n = 54)	Zoobenthos (n = 6)	LOCB Pellet (n = 1)	Wheat (n = 1)	Carp fillet* (n = 50)
C10:0	0.02 \pm 0.01	NS	0.01	0.02	NS
C11:0	0.15 \pm 0.30	NS	-	-	NS
C12:0	0.21 \pm 0.16	NS	0.02	0.02	0.03 \pm 0.01
C13:0	0.21 \pm 0.26	NS	-	-	0.03 \pm 0.01
C14:0	3.66 \pm 0.81	0.73 \pm 0.51	0.16	0.16	0.89 \pm 0.08
C14:1	0.13 \pm 0.30	0.92 \pm 0.67	-	-	0.06 \pm 0.01
C15:0	1.23 \pm 0.29	NS	0.08	0.12	0.18 \pm 0.04
C15:1	0.10 \pm 0.02	NS	-	-	-
C16:0	19.07 \pm 1.64	15.26 \pm 2.73	10.69	17.04	18.16 \pm 1.26
C16:1	9.07 \pm 3.16	4.15 \pm 2.74	0.64	0.28	7.40 \pm 1.11
C17:0	1.91 \pm 0.55	NS	0.17	0.13	0.18 \pm 0.04
C17:1	0.10 \pm 0.06	NS	-	-	-
C18:0	5.11 \pm 1.24	13.33 \pm 2.27	4.41	1.28	5.34 \pm 0.50
C18:1n-9 trans	0.24 \pm 0.08	NS	0.15	-	0.27 \pm 0.08
C18:1n-9	8.65 \pm 2.65	11.35 \pm 9.30	38.53	13.07	44.04 \pm 2.62
C18:1n-7	3.08 \pm 0.60	8.58 \pm 3.99	5.48	0.95	3.60 \pm 0.34
C18:2n-6 trans	0.18 \pm 0.00	NS	-	-	-
C18:2n-6	5.06 \pm 1.49	8.21 \pm 5.70	32.83	60.36	10.41 \pm 2.21
C18:3n-6	0.57 \pm 0.14	NS	-	-	0.27 \pm 0.06
C18:3n-3	12.88 \pm 2.34	13.08 \pm 8.88	5.02	5.06	1.65 \pm 0.48
C20:0	0.21 \pm 0.05	0.97 \pm 0.72	0.46	0.15	0.14 \pm 0.03
C20:1n-9	0.26 \pm 0.10	0.61 \pm 0.38	0.60	0.63	2.05 \pm 0.26
C21:0	0.02 \pm 0.02	NS	0.01	0.01	NS
C20:2n-6	0.24 \pm 0.11	1.48 \pm 1.58	0.05	0.08	NS
C20:3n-6	0.37 \pm 0.16	NS	-	-	0.49 \pm 0.11
C20:4n-6	3.08 \pm 1.21	5.14 \pm 4.08	-	-	1.48 \pm 0.33
C20:3n-3	0.57 \pm 0.28	1.15 \pm 1.00	-	-	0.10 \pm 0.04
C22:0	0.10 \pm 0.04	0.38 \pm 0.28	0.30	0.20	0.06 \pm 0.02
C22:1n-9	0.12 \pm 0.05	-	0.07	0.08	0.07 \pm 0.02
C20:5n-3	15.54 \pm 3.95	12.01 \pm 5.67	-	-	0.92 \pm 0.27
C22:2n-6	-	NS	-	-	0.03 \pm 0.01
C24:0	0.09 \pm 0.04	0.54 \pm 0.32	0.20	0.20	-
C24:1n-9	0.14 \pm 0.06	-	0.16	0.16	0.07 \pm 0.02
C22:5n-3	0.76 \pm 0.40	3.07 \pm 0.77	-	-	0.42 \pm 0.12
C22:6n-3	7.46 \pm 5.90	1.12 \pm 0.79	-	-	1.44 \pm 0.50
Lipid (%DM)	10.05 \pm 2.21	0.73 \pm 0.37	2.37	1.23	6.66 \pm 2.49

* No significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in omega-3 profile was found between carp fillets from wheat and LOCB-plant pellet fed group; hence, the pooled values of fillet ($n = 50$), represented here.

3.7. Impact of biotic and abiotic factors on omega-3 fatty acid availability

In the principal component analysis (PCA) (Fig. 5), the first two dimensions (Dim1: 39.7 %; Dim2: 20.1 %) collectively explained 59.8 % of total variance. Dim1 showed a cluster of strongly positively loaded variables, including TN concentration, chl-*a* (eutrophication proxy), and fish mass density (fish predation pressure proxy). Conversely, negatively and strongly loaded variables (Dim1), including lipid, ALA, and EPA availability, clustered with cladoceran abundance. However, the vector for DHA availability rotated noticeably away from this tight, negatively loaded cluster (Dim1) toward the direction of the positive end of Dim2, suggesting additional, separate (apart from cladocera) weak control on DHA availability, which is related to DOC and TP concentration. Additionally, the abundance of copepods did not show any association with the negatively loaded cluster of Dim1 (particularly, DM, lipid, ALA, and EPA).

3.8. Influence of feeding regimes on lipid and fatty acid supply from planktonic natural food

There was no influence of different supplementary feeding regimes on the lipid and fatty acids quantity available from planktonic natural food. Plankton consortia from group-1 and group-2 ponds did not differ in dry matter, lipid, ALA, EPA, DHA, n-3 PUFA and n-6 PUFA concentrations ($p > 0.05$; Table 2).

4. Discussion

The escalating demand for essential omega-3 LCPUFAs underscores the limitations of marine fisheries (Hamilton et al., 2020) and highlights the need to diversify sources, especially in landlocked regions, such as central Europe (see introduction), with no immediate accessibility to marine resources. However, the central and eastern European region (CEER) possesses huge freshwater resources in the

Fig. 5. PCA biplot between limnological parameters and availability of Lipid (including EPA, DHA, and ALA) in ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$). FMD: fish mass density (g m^{-3}), Chl-a: Chlorophyll a concentration ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), DM availability: Dry matter $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$.

Table 2

Availability of dry matter, lipid, and fatty acids from planktonic food web to carp under different pond feeding regimes.

Parameter	Group-1 pond (n = 3)	Group-2 pond (n = 6)	p-value
Dry matter (mg l^{-1})	0.68 ± 0.51	0.68 ± 0.59	0.7342
Lipid ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	71.50 ± 53.01	70.71 ± 65.79	0.6398
ALA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	8.13 ± 6.35	9.00 ± 8.63	0.8761
EPA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	8.55 ± 6.35	8.13 ± 7.02	0.6268
DHA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	3.78 ± 3.78	2.69 ± 2.68	0.3735
n-3 PUFA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	21.16 ± 14.91	20.38 ± 17.87	0.5757
n-6 PUFA ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	5.57 ± 4.13	5.70 ± 5.41	0.5387

form of ponds (Roy et al., 2025), but freshwater pond food webs are frequently criticized as nutritionally inferior (Matsushita et al., 2020; Pilecky et al., 2022; Roy et al., 2023a) and often ignored as a source of important lipids. It is probably due to the poor yield ($<250 \text{ mg } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ carp fillet) of these important lipids for the human food system (Linhartová et al., 2018). Counter to this paradigm, our analysis reveals that a considerable amount of EPA+DHA ($1785.78 \pm 479.30 \text{ mg } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ DM) is available as in trophic transferable form (carp-gill filterable Plankton consortia) in CEER ponds. Additionally, the different fish feed applications have no feed-mediated effect on the quantity of lipids and fatty acids available from planktonic natural food, which are primarily governed by various ecological factors of the pond (discussed later). However, the constraint is the temporal heterogeneity in the availability of these lipids in the ponds. This likely results in bioenergetics mismatch-driven inefficiency in bioaccumulation of Omega-3 LCPUFAs (only 30 %) in traditionally farmed carp (discussed below) and, consequently, shrinks its path to the human food system.

4.1. The impact of seasonal lipid availability on carp EPA+DHA accumulation

At the beginning season, peak availability of lipid and omega-3 PUFAs indicates an abundant supply. In contrast, at the end season, all of them showed minimum availability, underscoring the scarcity of important lipids for consumers (carp) (Fig. 2). In addition to this, FA stoichiometric insights (Fig. 3) underscore a significantly higher omega-3 (EPA+DHA) sparing effect in the beginning season compared to the end season. Hence, it is conclusive that during the period of the beginning season (May–July), carp could easily build up their EPA+DHA reserves, benefiting from both an abundant supply of these PUFAs and a higher availability of energy lipids (SFA & MUFA) to spare the reserves from catabolism, as fish preferred to catabolize SFA or MUFA over the PUFAs (Rombenso et al., 2022). Conversely, throughout the end season (August–September), they were constrained by a lower supply of these omega-3 PUFAs. Instead of having the availability of more refined lipids (n-3: n-6 ratio of 4.42), it showed a reduced omega-3 sparing effect. Hence, carp likely had to rely on their stored omega-3 (EPA+DHA) to meet their energy needs, which could result in lower retention and a lower EPA+DHA concentration in carp at the end of the season (November) harvest. EPA and ALA have almost identical trends, while the DHA trend is slightly different from them (Fig. 2); unlike EPA and ALA, DHA availability is constrained not only at the end of the season but also at the very early beginning season (May). While the impact of this early beginning season limitation (less DHA accumulation) could be diluted by higher availability in the following two months (June–July), while the end season (August–October) limit warrants serious concern. A low supply of overall omega-3 PUFAs over this final and longer three-month period might result in a net dilution of omega-3 concentration in the fish.

EPA and DHA are not the essential FAs for carp (NRC, 1993); during the scarcity of these FAs (e.g., end season), it could synthesize them from precursor FAs, ALA (Monroig et al., 2022; Pilecky et al., 2022; Roy et al., 2023a), which indicates a theoretical possibility for EPA+DHA yield at the end season. Nevertheless, modeling of ALA supply vs. demands (Fig. 4) indicates that the supply from natural food (plankton consortia and zoobenthos) becomes inadequate to meet carp's minimum ALA requirements (0.5 %) (NRC, 1993) Remain insufficient throughout the end season (August–October) in ponds. In addition to this, wheat supplementation is (in optimum feeding rate) also inefficient to meet the demand in the terminal months (end season). Cumulative ALA provision from wheat and natural sources in the end season constitutes only ~26.7 % (mean) of the total requirement. Therefore, the synergistic inability of carp to accumulate, protect, and biosynthesize EPA and DHA (in the last 3 months before harvest) ultimately leads to a reduction in their concentration and results in lower EPA+DHA yield.

4.2. Ecological drivers of omega-3 PUFAs availability in Regional Fishponds

In Principal component (Fig. 5), the positively loaded cluster in Dim1 explained that EPA, ALA, and total lipid availability were positively linked to DM of plankton consortia and particularly to cladoceran abundance, which corroborates a previous study (Hessen and Leu, 2006). Lipid class analysis indicates that, throughout the end the season, the gill-filterable plankton consortia prioritize maintaining structural lipids (phosphatidylcholine) over storage lipids (triglycerides) (Fig. 2e & f), which are predominantly composed of less saturated fatty acids. In this consortium, zooplanktons are also observed to maintain body length throughout the season, despite a loss of dry matter at the end of the season (Fig. 1d, g & h). These findings clearly indicate an overwintering preparation strategy among zooplankton groups, whereby they preferentially retain structural lipids rich in unsaturated FAs (with lower melting point) to preserve cellular and structural integrity (Werner et al., 2021). In addition, this consortium maintains consistent cholesterol levels throughout the season (Fig. 2f). This behavior is characteristic of cladoceran zooplankton, for which cholesterol is indispensable (Benjami Laine et al., 2024). Therefore, in contrast to copepods, cladocera act as the key regulator of trophically transferable EPA and ALA availability (to some extent, DHA as well) in the CEER pond system. The positively loaded cluster on Dim1 (Fig. 5) indicates a trophic cascade-mediated eutrophication process, which negatively impacts the previously described cluster, particularly its EPA and ALA availability. The end-season increase in a zooplankton predation proxy (FMD) (Fig. 1e) and the collapse of the cladoceran population suggest a strong top-down control (Yin et al., 2025). Concurrently, increasing chlorophyll a (Fig. 1f), indicates a parallel bottom-up eutrophication effect (Roy et al., 2022). Therefore, the overall results suggest that EPA and ALA availability are primarily dependent on cladoceran abundance and are negatively regulated by the combined effects of eutrophication and top-down predation. However, the distant positioning of the DHA vector from the EPA and ALA cluster (Dim1) (Fig. 5) suggests a different regulatory mechanism for DHA availability (only weak positive regulation by cladocera, DOC and TP). It might suggest a algae/ DHA rich phytoplankton (diatoms) (Schagerl et al., 2025) driven DHA contribution apart from Cladocera. It is due to observed presence of glycolipids (structural lipids of algae) in the plankton consortium, and their decreasing trend and lower availability in end season (Fig. 2e), which corroborates the DHA trend (Fig. 2d).

4.3. A conceptual framework for sustainable EPA+DHA mining from pond aquaculture

This study clearly demarcates an end-season window (August–October) characterized by a critical lack of omega-3 availability. Prolonging the abundance of large-bodied cladocerans and reducing carp-mediated nutrient loading are crucial during this period to maintain omega-3 levels. Several previous studies suggest that strategies such as the "balanced feeding concept" (Roy et al., 2022) and promoting submerged vegetation (Tang et al., 2021) could be applied in this regard. Furthermore, during this seasonal window, the carp's food web lacks non-PUFA lipid energy to spare natural food-driven EPA+DHA reserves. Traditionally supplemented wheat is high in starch carbohydrate, which results in starch-mediated de novo lipogenesis (SFA synthesis). This makes carp fatty in the end season but not rich in EPA+DHA (Csengeri, 1996), as they lack the methyl-end desaturase ($\Delta 12$ & $\Delta 15$) to produce PUFAs directly from glucose (Monroig et al., 2022). Starch-mediated PUFA sparing is ineffective for carp but could be achievable by supplementing

non-PUFA lipid energy. Pond carp begin preparing for overwintering in the end season, and the EPA+DHA biosynthesis pathway from ALA precursors becomes more active (Roy et al., 2023b). However, this study showed that the limited ALA supply from both natural and supplementary food in traditional farming practices offsets the theoretical potential for EPA+DHA production. Hence, this study warrants a reform in traditional end-of-season (August–October) feeding management. Supplementing with non-PUFA lipid energy and leveraging the biosynthesis pathway by providing precursor ALA from plant-based ingredients could enhance the EPA+DHA mining potential of semi-intensive CEER ponds without the use of marine ingredients.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that central and eastern European pond ecosystems, though long regarded as nutritionally limited, contain substantial trophic transferable reservoirs of omega-3 LCPUFAs. Seasonal analyses revealed strong temporal heterogeneity, with peak EPA + DHA availability early in the production cycle (May–July) and pronounced depletion during the end-season (August–October). This decline, driven by reduced cladoceran abundance and eutrophication, constrains the trophic transfer of omega-3 lipids and limits carp bioaccumulation efficiency. The simultaneous deficit of ALA precursors further restricts endogenous synthesis of EPA and DHA, along with a low omega-sparing effect, resulting in a net seasonal decline in fish omega-3 yield.

To overcome this bioenergetic bottleneck, management strategies should focus on maintaining large-bodied cladoceran populations, mitigating eutrophication, and reforming end-season feeding practices either with fish oil-based finishing feed (EPA+DHA rich) or a vegetable oil-based plant feed (ALA rich) at least three months before harvest. Providing non-PUFA lipid energy alongside ALA-rich oil source could enhance PUFA sparing and biosynthetic conversion, increasing EPA and DHA in carp fillets. Maintenance of stable zooplankton-benthos population in ponds by providing environmental enrichments such as littoral macrophyte beds or by balanced pond feeding approach would act as trophic transfer agents of nature's regenerative EPA+DHA from food web to carp flesh. Overall, these findings establish a mechanistic link between pond ecology and fish lipid metabolism, offering a framework to optimize omega-3 production in semi-intensive freshwater aquaculture.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ales Tomcala: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Deepali Rahi Roy:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Koushik Roy:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Bidipta Mandal:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jan Mraz:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

OpenAI “Data analyst” was used for data analysis, visualizations in tandem with RStudio. Authors declare no other competing interests.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

Technical guidance of Ms. Zdenka Machova assisting in the lipid biochemistry of plankton consortia is gratefully acknowledged. Dr. Petr Dvorak is gratefully acknowledged for assisting the field sampling. The study was funded by the Czech Science Foundation (GAČR 22-18597S) and Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic, OP JAK – Aquaculture for Future project (CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0012616).

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2026.116678](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2026.116678).

Data availability

Dataset and the readme file are made available in supplementary material (.zip).

References

- Anton-Pardo, M., Hlaváč, D., Másilko, J., Hartman, P., Adámek, Z., 2014. Natural diet of mirror and scaly carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) phenotypes in earth ponds. *Folia Zool.* 63 (4), 229–237.
- Appelqvist, L.-Å., 1968. Rapid methods of lipid extraction and fatty acid methyl ester preparation for seed and leaf tissue with special remarks on preventing the accumulation of lipid contaminants. *Ark. F. öR. kemi* 28 (36), 551–570.
- Benjami Laine, M., Martin-Creuzburg, D., Litmanen, J.J., Taipale, S.J., 2024. Sterol limitation of *Daphnia* on eukaryotic phytoplankton: a combined supplementation and compound-specific stable isotope labeling approach. *Oikos* 2024 (6), e10359.
- Csengeri, I., 1996. Dietary effects on fatty acid metabolism of common carp. *Arch. Anim. Nutr.* 49 (1), 73–92.
- Gordon, D.V., Bjørndal, T., 2009. A comparative study of production factors and productivity for shrimp farms in three Asian countries: Bangladesh, India, and Indonesia. *Aquac. Econ. Manag.* 13 (2), 176–190.
- Hamilton, H.A., Newton, R., Auchterlonie, N.A., Müller, D.B., 2020. Systems approach to quantify the global omega-3 fatty acid cycle. *Nat. Food* 1 (1), 59–62.
- Hara, A., Radin, N.S., 1978. Lipid extraction of tissues with a low-toxicity solvent. *Anal. Biochem.* 90 (1), 420–426.
- Hasan, M., Macintosh, D., 1992. Optimum food particle size in relation to body size of common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* L., fry. *Aquac. Res.* 23 (3), 315–325.
- Hessen, D.O., Leu, E., 2006. Trophic transfer and trophic modification of fatty acids in high Arctic lakes. *Freshw. Biol.* 51 (11), 1987–1998.
- Kainz, M.J., Hager, H.H., Rasconi, S., Kahilainen, K.K., Amundsen, P.A., Hayden, B., 2017. Polyunsaturated fatty acids in fishes increase with total lipids irrespective of feeding sources and trophic position. *Ecosphere* 8 (4), e01753.
- Kajgrova, L., Adámek, Z., Regenda, J., Bauer, C., Stejskal, V., Pecha, O., Hlavac, D., 2021. Macrozoobenthos assemblage patterns in European carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) ponds—the importance of emerged macrophyte beds. *Knowl. Manag. Aquat. Ecosyst.* 422, 9.
- Kajgrova, L., Blabolil, P., Drozd, B., Roy, K., Regenda, J., Šorf, M., Vrba, J., 2022. Negative effects of undesirable fish on common carp production and overall structure and functioning of fishpond ecosystems. *Aquaculture* 549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737811>.
- Linhartová, Z., Krejsa, J., Zajíc, T., Másilko, J., Sampels, S., Mráz, J., 2018. Proximate and fatty acid composition of 13 important freshwater fish species in central Europe. *Aquac. Int.* 26, 695–711.
- Matsushita, Y., Miyoshi, K., Kabeya, N., Sanada, S., Yazawa, R., Haga, Y., Satoh, S., Yamamoto, Y., Strüssmann, C.A., Luckenbach, J.A., 2020. Flatfishes colonised freshwater environments by acquisition of various DHA biosynthetic pathways. *Commun. Biol.* 3 (1), 516.
- Monroig, Ó., Shu-Chien, A., Kabeya, N., Tocher, D.R., Castro, L.F.C., 2022. Desaturases and elongases involved in long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acid biosynthesis in aquatic animals: From genes to functions. *Prog. Lipid Res.* 86, 101157.
- Mraz, J., Pickova, J., 2009. Differences between lipid content and composition of different parts of filets from crossbred farmed carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *Fish. Physiol. Biochem.* 35 (4), 615–623. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-008-9291-5>.
- Mraz, J., Pickova, J., 2011. Factors influencing fatty acid composition of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) muscle. *Neuroendocrinol. Lett.* 32 (2), 3–8.
- Mraz, J., Máčková, J., Kozák, P., Pickova, J., 2012. Lipid content and composition in common carp—optimization of n-3 fatty acids in different pond production systems. *J. Appl. Ichthyol.* 28 (2), 238–244.
- Mraz, J., Mandal, B., Vrba, J., Kajgrova, L., Blaha, M., Kuebutornye, F.K.A., Zabransky, L., Nahlik, V., Lepic, P., Roy, K., 2025. Nutritional requirement of European fishponds to achieve low and efficient feed use avoiding eutrophication. *Aquaculture*, 743389.
- Mráz, J., Zajíc, T., Pickova, J., 2012. Culture of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) with defined flesh quality for prevention of cardiovascular diseases using finishing feeding strategy. *Neuroendocrinol. Lett.* 33 (2), 60–67.
- NRC, N.R.C., 1993. Nutrient requirements of fish. National Academy Press, Washington DC.
- OECD/European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2017. Czech Republic: Country Health Profile 2017, State of Health in the EU. OECD Publishing, Paris/European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, Brussels. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264283336-en>.
- Olsen, R., Henderson, R., 1989. The rapid analysis of neutral and polar marine lipids using double-development HPTLC and scanning densitometry. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 129 (2), 189–197.
- Pilecky, M., Mathieu-Resuge, M., Závorka, L., Fehlinger, L., Winter, K., Martin-Creuzburg, D., Kainz, M.J., 2022. Common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) obtain omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids via dietary supply and endogenous bioconversion in semi-intensive aquaculture ponds. *Aquaculture* 561, 738731.
- Rombenso, A.N., Turchini, G.M., Trushenski, J.T., 2022. The omega-3 sparing effect of saturated fatty acids: A reason to reconsider common knowledge of fish oil replacement. *Rev. Aquac.* 14 (1).
- Roy, K., Vrba, J., Kajgrova, L., Mraz, J., 2022. The concept of balanced fish nutrition in temperate European fishponds to tackle eutrophication. *J. Clean. Prod.* 364, 132584.
- Roy, K., Dvorak, P., Machova, Z., Mraz, J., 2023a. Nutrient footprint versus EPA+ DHA security in land-locked regions—more of local pond farmed, imported marine fish or fish oil capsules? *npj Sci. Food* 7 (1), 48.
- Roy, K., Másilko, J., Kajgrova, L., Kuebutornye, F.K.A., Oberle, M., Mraz, J., 2023b. End-of-season supplementary feeding in European carp ponds with appropriate plant protein and carbohydrate combinations to ecologically boost productivity: lupine, rapeseed and, triticale. *Aquaculture* 577, 739906.
- Roy, K., Verdegem, M.C., Mraz, J., 2025. Ecological Restoration of Inland Aquaculture in Land-Locked Europe: The Role of Semi-Intensive Fishponds and Multitrophic Technologies in Transforming Food Systems. *Rev. Aquac.* 17 (1), e12999.
- Schagerl, M., Yen, C.-C., Bauer, C., Gaspar, L., Waringer, J., 2025. Fishponds Are Hotspots of Algal Biodiversity—Organic Carp Farming Reveals Unexpected High Taxa Richness. *Environments* 12 (3), 92.
- Schuchardt, J.P., Beinhorn, P., Hu, X.F., Chan, H.M., Roke, K., Bernasconi, A., Hahn, A., Sala Vila, A., Stark, K.D., Harris, W.S., 2024. Omega-3 world map: 2024 update.
- Sibbing, F.A., 1988. Specializations and limitations in the utilization of food resources by the carp, *Cyprinus carpio*: a study of oral food processing. *Environ. Biol. Fishes* 22 (3), 161–178.
- Tang, Y., Zhou, D., Su, L., Liu, Z., Zhang, X., Dumont, H.J., 2021. *Vallisneria natans* detritus supports *Daphnia magna* somatic growth and reproduction under addition of periphyton. *Aquat. Ecol.* 55, 579–588.
- Vrba, J., Šorf, M., Nedoma, J., Benedová, Z., Kroepfelová, L., Sulcová, J., Tesarova, B., Musil, M., Pechar, L., Potuzák, J., Regenda, J., Simek, K., Reháková, K., 2024. Top-down and bottom-up control of plankton structure and dynamics in hypertrophic fishponds. *Hydrobiologia* 851 (5), 1095–1111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-023-05312-5>.
- Werner, C., Otte, K.A., von Elert, E., 2021. Phenotypic convergence in a natural *Daphnia* population acclimated to low temperature. *Ecol. Evol.* 11 (21), 15312–15324.
- Xu, H., Turchini, G.M., Francis, D.S., Liang, M., Mock, T.S., Rombenso, A., Ai, Q., 2020. Are fish what they eat? A fatty acid's perspective. *Prog. Lipid Res.* 80, 101064.
- Yin, C., Gong, L., Yang, J., Yang, Y., Guo, L., 2025. Spatial-Seasonal Shifts in Phytoplankton and Zooplankton Community Structure Within a Subtropical Plateau Lake: Interplay with Environmental Drivers During Rainy and Dry Seasons. *Fishes* 10 (7), 343.
- Zárate, R., el Jaber-Vazdekis, N., Tejera, N., Pérez, J.A., Rodríguez, C., 2017. Significance of long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids in human health. *Clin. Transl. Med.* 6 (1), 25.